

Full-Duplex mmWave/FSO Transmission over Shared Aperture with Optical Focal Plane Array Feed

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Abstract: We show mm-wave/FSO transmission over a shared antenna aperture with multi-core fiber feed. Full-duplex 10Gb/s FSO and OFDM transmission at 26.5/33.7GHz is proven for a fiber-wireless link, using a simplified EAM transceiver at the fronthaul. © 2026 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Free-space optics (FSO) is an integral part of the 6G x-haul and access segments as it bears the potential to transport high Tb/s capacities. However, FSO propagation is impaired under poor atmospheric conditions, including beam wander or spread in presence of turbulence, strong power fading due to fog and rain, or beam blocking by snow [1]. Even though part of these can be mitigated through beamforming [2, 3] or signal conversion to a mid-infrared waveband [4], the typically simpler and more practical co-integration of optical and wireless systems [5] renders hybrid FSO/RF transmission a compelling weather-tolerant [6, 7] solution. Nonetheless, providing a compact and low-complexity FSO/RF system becomes a formidable challenge. Towards that, a simplification of the air interface towards integrating two antennas into a single one with shared aperture – enabling FSO and RF links simultaneously without degrading the performance of the individual links – has been demonstrated by means of dichroic THz/FSO filters [8], partially transparent up-conversion photodiodes [9] or lensed FR3/FSO horn antennas [10].

In this work we advance lensed horn antennas for FR2 operation to show full-duplex mm-wave transmission and a multi-core fiber (MCF) feed for the FSO air interface. We employ an EAM transceiver element as simplified fronthaul interface for the remote radio head (RRH) for both, 25.3/34.2 GHz mm-wave and 10 Gb/s FSO modes.

2. Hybrid mm-Wave / FSO Transmission over Shared Aperture

Figure 1 presents the experimental setup. For **RF transmission**, the 1-GHz down- (DL) and uplink (UL) OFDM signals are converted from an IF of 5 GHz to the DL/UL carriers at 34.2 / 25.3 GHz, using mm-wave converters at the central office (CO) and tail-end terminal (TET). The DL transmitter at the CO builds on a MZM and interleaver (I/L) to suppress one sideband. The UL is received with an EDFA+PIN receiver. Red/blue (R/B) waveband splitters realize the directional split between DL and UL. The fronthaul is furnished with a 13.2-km single-mode fiber (SMF). Two RRHs are evaluated: The first (**I**) builds on colored optics with dedicated receiver and EML transmitter. The radio signals are conditioned through electrical amplifiers (EA) and a duplexer (DPX) accommodates frequency division duplexing (FDD) for full-duplex transmission over the air interface. The second RRH configuration (**II**) employs a SOA-amplified EAM as a colorless optical transceiver for electro-optic conversion of DL and UL. A DPX at the common EAM port facilitates a crosstalk suppressing directional FDD split and a simple directional coupler (CPL) is employed at the air interface due to the shortage of further DPX elements. After lab-scale (3.7 m) over-the-air transmission, a combination of CPL and bandpass filter (BPF) is used at the TET to realize a directional split between DL and UL branches, before down-conversion of the OFDM signal takes place for EVM evaluation.

For **FSO transmission** a MCF with 7 uncoupled single-mode cores pitched by 35 μm serves as a multi-aperture air interface to enable alignment-tolerant coupling through a focal plane-array configuration [10]. For this, a set of 7 wavelengths ($\lambda_1 \dots \lambda_7$) is jointly modulated with 10 Gb/s OOK at the CO. The set is then demultiplexed with a cyclic (800 GHz) 1×8 AWG at the RRH to feed the MCF cores (i.e., antenna elements) at the cross-section of the focal plane of a 2" lens attached to the shared-aperture horn antenna (Fig. 1). The TET receives at least one wavelength channel carrying the DL, even under sub-optimal alignment [10]. The BER is tested after photodetection by an APD. A tunable EML is modulated at 10 Gb/s for UL transmission. To ensure good FSO coupling, the TET is required to choose a cyclic

wavelength that is linked to the optimal MCF core at the RRH. This information can be extracted by appending a channel-specific pilot tone f_i to each of the DL wavelengths. The UL is then tuned to the corresponding channel and detected at the CO by an APD. For the sake of experimental simplicity, the FSO mode has been sequentially evaluated to the RF mode, re-using the C-band centric R/B wavelength plan with the (blue) DL being allocated on a set from $\lambda_1 = 1538.4$ to $\lambda_7 = 1543.2$ nm, while the (red) UL channel is above 1544.1 nm.

Figure 2(a) reports the S-parameters over WR28 waveguide adapters and shared-aperture air interfaces with 13-dBi horn antennas. There is no notable impact on the response when introducing the fiber port to the waveguide-to-coax adapter (dotted/dashed curves). The addition of an optical lens to the horn antennas leads to a ripple of up to 1.6 and 2.1 dB over the DL and UL OFDM ranges. Figures 2b and 2c show the optical fronthaul spectra at the RRH for the RF transmission mode with remote-modulation RRH (*II*), where DL and a CW seed are jointly supplied to the EAM. The mm-wave DL at 1532.03 nm (Fig. 2b) is detected by the EAM and experiences a not further relevant re-modulation by the UL. For the UL at 1559.89 nm, Fig. 2c shows the CW seed carrier and the remotely modulated UL signal at the SOA output. Despite the presence of the optical DL signal that is jointly amplified by the SOA, there is no cross-gain modulation of the UL signal. The RF signal spectra along the bidirectional RRH chain are shown in Fig. 2d for RRH configuration *II*, together with the transmission windows T of the DPX and BPFs. The 34-GHz DL after reception by the EAM (point 1 in Fig. 1) shows little crosstalk by the boosted 25-GHz UL, by virtue of the good rejection through the DPX. Note that due to the TIA-less EAM, the DL signal enhances above the measurement noise floor after the EA (2). The UL that is received at the RRH air interface (3) shows significant DL crosstalk, given that a simple RF coupler is used for the directional split. This crosstalk requires an additional BPF for its suppression (4). Again, the UL signal rises above the measurement floor after the EA (5). It shall be stressed that the close alignment of the DL to the 33-GHz cross-over of the DPX is a result of the roll-off in EAM response.

3. Transmission Results in RF and FSO Modes

Figure 3a reports the EVM for DL reception at the TET in **RF transmission mode**, shown for half-duplex back-to-back (b2b) transmission without (Δ) and with (\diamond) optical lens. There is no significant penalty, attributing the ripple in EVM to the chain of EAs and BPFs. Figure 3b presents the DL EVM as a function of the received optical power (ROP) at the RRH receiver. For RRH configuration *I* in half-duplex b2b transmission (\diamond) we obtain a low average EVM of 6.2% and the limit of 12.5% for 16-QAM sub-carrier modulation is surpassed at -11.8 dBm. This moderate ROP trades optical link budget with a simplified RRH that omits optical preamplification. There is neither a penalty for full-duplex operation (\blacklozenge) nor for the 13.2 km fronthaul (\circ, \bullet). For RRH *II* with EAM as transceiver, we still accomplish a low EVM of 6.9% for the half-duplex fronthaul (Δ). The increase of the ROP to -3.8 dBm at the EVM limit is a result of TIA-less EAM operation. The penalty of 0.9 dB in full-duplex mode (\blacktriangle) is caused by crosstalk from the UL booster EA of the TET to its DL receiver, which could be avoided by replacing its directional CPL with a DPX. Figure 3d compares the 16-QAM constellations of the DL for both RRHs in half-/full-duplex modes. Figure 3c shows the EVM for UL transmission. For RRH *I* we obtain a half-duplex b2b EVM of 7.3% (\diamond). The EVM limit is surpassed at -19.5 dBm for the EDFA+PIN receiver at the CO. We see a degradation of 0.2% in EVM and 2.7 dB in ROP at the EVM limit over fronthaul (\circ), which is attributed to the interplay of EML chirp and dispersion. There are no notable penalties for full-duplex operation (\blacklozenge, \bullet) in either case. For RRH *II*, the 1.5% increase in half-duplex b2b EVM (\square) is explained by increased noise (loss in RF chain, SOA). Full-duplex UL reception incurs an 0.6% penalty, while fronthaul transmission causes another $\sim 0.9\%$ (Δ, \blacktriangle) due to Rayleigh backscattering of the CW seed carrier along the single, bidirectional fiber span. Still, the accomplished EVM is well below the 12.5% limit.

FSO transmission mode: Figure 4a presents the λ -set of the DL as well as the UL channel in the blue and red wavebands. Only one of the DL wavelengths, λ_2 , couples off-center with a FSO path loss of 13.1 dB (w/o AWG and MCF fan-in). Figure 4b shows the corresponding λ -specific coupling at the launched channels over the MCF-based focal plane. This proves robust FSO coupling through the MCF feed, whereas a purely SMF-based air interface (i.e., only center core) would face an extra loss of 21.6 dB. As reported in Fig. 4c, the reception of λ_2 through the λ -agnostic APD at the TET is indicated by the received pilot at $f_2 = 223$ kHz, just above the low-frequency cut-off of the receiver and below the data harmonics. This tone features a SNR of 40 dB for a low intensity modulation ER of 0.2 dB. The 10 Gb/s FSO DL performance is shown in Fig. 4d. Without pilot, the sensitivities at the TET are -26.3 and -26.0 dBm for a fronthaul without (\circ) and with (\bullet) SMF. The impact of the pilot is assessed in Fig. 4e, showing

the BER at a ROP of -26.3 dBm as a function of the pilot ER. The slight increase in BER for an ER of 0.14 dB (SNR of 32.6 dB) leads to an offset in ROP of ~ 0.45 dB (from Fig. 4d). The 10 Gb/s FSO UL performance is appended to Fig. 4d. We obtain a sensitivity of -24.7 dBm at the CO receiver for the b2b case (Δ). Furnishing the fronthaul with 13.2 km leads to a penalty of 2.6 dB (\blacktriangle), which is attributed to chirped EML modulation at high extinction.

4. Conclusion

We have demonstrated full-duplex 16-QAM OFDM transmission over $25.3/34.2$ GHz mm-wave carriers and 10 Gb/s FSO transmission over a shared-aperture air interface that seamlessly integrates an FR2 horn antenna with a focal-plane array FSO interface. The MCF feed at the RRH enables to maintain FSO communication even under sub-optimal alignment, while pilot-assisted wavelength steering retains a simple, SMF-based tail-end design.

5. References

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Fig. 1. Experimental setup for mm-wave / FSO transmission. The insets show the MCF plane at the air interface and the shared-aperture antenna.

Fig. 2. (a) S-parameters for shared-aperture antenna. (b) Optical fronthaul spectra for mm-wave mode. (c) Spectra within the RF chain of RRH II.

Fig. 3. RF transmission mode: (a) Impact of lens on half-duplex DL EVM, (b) DL EVM and (c) UL EVM performance. (d) DL constellations.

Fig. 4. FSO mode: (a) Spectra over FSO link and (b) coupled MCF cores, (c) pilot tone at TET, (d) BER performance and (e) impact of pilot.